

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods

Variations in anther culture-derived lines of Ponni

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We studied 10 lines derived by anther culture from Ponni (Mahsuri) in a randomized block design with 3 replications Dec 1986-May 1987. The anther culture-derived lines showed drastic reduction in duration, plant height, and grain yield but increased

Performance of anther culture-derived lines. Coimbatore, India, 1986-87.

Entry	Days to flowering	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Production (kg) per day
AC12	108	81	6.6	24.4	17.5	3.8	27.5
AC13	109	79	6.9	24.7	17.5	4.7	33.8
AC14	108	80	8.1	21.5	17.1	4.3	31.2
AC15	108	81	7.9	24.4	17.1	5.0	36.2
AC16	107	83	8.3	23.8	17.5	5.3	38.7
AC17	109	82	7.9	23.3	17.6	4.9	35.3
AC18	109	81	7.5	23.9	17.6	4.9	35.3
AC19	110	84	7.7	23.6	17.1	4.2	30.0
AC20	110	81	7.9	23.2	17.3	4.5	32.1
AC21	107	84	8.5	24.5	17.6	4.7	34.3
Ponni	122	121	6.1	26.9	14.8	7.0	46.1
m+σ	114	—	—	—	—	—	—
LSD (P=0.05)	—	6	ns	ns	0.1	1.1	—
CV (%)	4	4	15.1	7.5	0.4	14.0	—

1,000-grain weight (see table). Panicle numbers and panicle lengths were not statistically different.

The lines derived from Ponni can be used as alternate genetic sources of shod stature in rice breeding. □

Yield potential

Weight and germination of main and ratoon crop seeds

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Studies in 1981-85 have indicated that ratooning rice under Kerala conditions is feasible. In 1986-87, we compared seed weight and germination of the main and ratoon crops of five varieties. Grain

Grain weight and germination of main and ratoon crop seeds. Pattambi, Kerala, India, 1986-87.

Variety	1000-grain weight (g)		Germination (%)	
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
BR51-315-4	23	19	96	97
BR52-96-3	25	22	96	98
Jaya	28	24	95	99
Pavizham	23	22	94	99
23332-2	20	21	92	98
LSD (P=0.05)	1		2	

was dried to 12% moisture and 1,000-grain weight estimated 1 mo after harvest. Germination was tested after 6-mo storage.

In spite of lower grain weights, ratoon crop seeds germinated as well as main crop seeds (see table). □

Metroglyph analysis of some upland rice cultures

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Morphological variations of 40 rice entries tested at the upland rice site in

1986 were studied using indexes and metroglyphs. Index values of range of variability were divided into four group using class intervals (see table). The two most variable traits (plant height and grain yield/plant) are depicted on the X- and Y-axes; other characters are represented by rays on the glyph (rays for the same trait have the same position on each glyph) (see figure). The performance of a particular entry is denoted by its index score.

Index scores for different traits of upland rice entries. Tamil Nadu, India.

Character	Range of means	Score 1 value <	Score 2	Score 3	Score 4 value >
Days to maturity	96.0 – 120.0	102	102.0 – 108	109	– 114
Tillers/plant	4.0 – 20	8	8 – 12	13	– 16
Grains/panicle	34.0 – 141	61	61 – 87	88	– 114
Root number	80.0 – 359	150	150 – 220	221	– 289
Root length (cm)	10.1 – 24.1	13.6	13.6 – 17.1	17.2	– 20.6
Root weight (g)	1.6 – 8.1	3.23	3.23 – 4.85	4.86	– 6.48
Dry matter production (g)	9.7 – 57.0	21.5	21.5 – 33.4	33.5	– 45.2
100-grain weight (g)	1.8 – 2.50	1.98	1.98 – 2.15	2.16	– 2.33